

UV-Enhanced Visual Inspection and AI-Based Assessment of Thermal Interface Material Application Quality

A dataset-driven case study for remote computer diagnostics

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Abstract

Thermal interface materials (TIMs), including high-performance thermal greases and high-conductivity viscous compounds, are critical enablers of heat dissipation in modern high-power electronics. In field deployments and repair scenarios, TIM degradation, voiding, or incomplete coverage can cause elevated junction temperatures, excessive fan operation, performance throttling, and accelerated component aging. Previous studies have quantified this correlation, demonstrating that prolonged thermal stress leads to measurable degradation in graphics performance under sustained workloads [21]. Despite this, the assessment of TIM application quality is still largely manual, technician-dependent, and difficult to standardize, especially in remote diagnostic workflows. This white paper proposes a practical approach for optical verification of TIM application using ultraviolet (UV) fluorescence, combined with artificial intelligence (AI)-ready data collection that enables computer vision methods to learn visual patterns associated with adequate or inadequate thermal contact. The approach is aligned with the broader scope of an AI-enabled remote computer diagnostic and data-recovery research project, where reliable fault triage, reproducible service procedures, and evidence-based decision-making are primary goals [19]. The paper contributes: (i) a multimodal dataset specification integrating UV/visible images and videos of TIM application, infrared (IR) thermography footage during controlled benchmark load, high-frequency telemetry logs, and benchmark outcomes; and (ii) an empirical case study demonstrating that thermal interface optimization materially affects graphics processing unit (GPU) and video random access memory (VRAM) peak temperatures, fan behavior, and benchmark performance under comparable load and board power. Benchmark and peak-thermal summary tables are included to quantify changes across the four experimental stages (before/after repaste under two fan profiles). The dataset associated with this research is published separately [18].

Keywords

thermal interface material (TIM), thermal contact resistance, UV fluorescence, optical inspection, computer vision, deep learning, infrared thermography, remote diagnostics, GPU thermals, dataset

1. Introduction

High-performance consumer and professional computing systems operate at sustained power levels that push thermal design limits. In these systems, the thermal path from heat-generating silicon to a heat sink is often dominated by interface effects: microscopic surface roughness, imperfect wetting, voids, and the mechanical evolution of the TIM layer under thermal cycling and clamping pressure. Both academic and industrial literature emphasize that interface thermal resistance can be a dominant contributor to overall junction-to-ambient resistance, particularly when bond-line thickness (BLT) and contact quality are suboptimal [1]–[4].

In field service and repair operations, TIM-related thermal contact issues are frequent yet difficult to assess remotely. Typical remote triage relies on telemetry (temperature, fan speed, clock behavior) and user-provided symptoms. This approach is necessary but often insufficient: telemetry can indicate overheating, but rarely provides direct evidence of root cause (for example, inadequate TIM coverage versus dust loading, fan curve misconfiguration, heatsink mounting pressure, or partial contact on memory/VRM regions). As a result, service outcomes may depend heavily on technician experience and iterative rework.

This white paper investigates a complementary diagnostic channel: UV-enhanced optical verification of TIM application, coupled with AI-ready data acquisition. The core premise is that, when TIM or an inspection-compatible fluorescent mechanism is visible under controlled UV illumination, coverage continuity becomes visually salient. This supports repeatable optical inspection, improves the feasibility of consistent annotation during dataset creation, and enables training of computer vision models that can classify application quality from a single image or a short video sequence. Detailed implementation specifics of any production inference pipeline are intentionally kept at a high level in this public version, consistent with intellectual property (IP) protection strategy, while preserving full scientific relevance to the research project scope and the documented empirical results.

2. Technical background and related work

2.1 Thermal contact resistance and TIM application quality

At the interface between two nominally flat solids (for example, a heat sink base and a package lid or die), real contact occurs only at asperity peaks; the remainder is void space typically filled with air, which has very low thermal conductivity. TIMs mitigate this by displacing air and improving effective contact conductance. In practical electronics cooling, the interface resistance can be decomposed into contact resistances at each surface plus bulk conduction through the TIM layer, which depends on BLT, thermal conductivity, pressure, surface roughness, and wetting behavior [1]–[4], [6]. Further research into specialized interconnect structures, such as semi-elastomeric thermally conductive interfaces, highlights the complexity of maintaining stable thermal paths in ball grid array (BGA) and printed circuit board (PCB) assemblies [20]. The literature also highlights challenges in reproducible TIM

testing and characterization and the limitations of direct comparison across vendor-reported conductivity values due to differences in reporting conventions and test conditions [3], [17].

From an applied diagnostics standpoint, incomplete TIM coverage and voiding have two properties that make them service-relevant:

- a) They can lead to localized hotspots, often visible in hotspot-adjacent sensors (for example, GPU hotspot and VRAM junction sensors).
- b) They can be visually detectable during assembly or rework if optical contrast is sufficiently high.

2.2 UV fluorescence as an inspection modality

Fluorescent inspection under UV illumination is well established in non-destructive testing, where fluorescent penetrant methods use UV-A excitation and visible emission to reveal small discontinuities and surface-connected defects [10], [11]. While TIM inspection is not identical to penetrant testing, the inspection principle is analogous: fluorescence can substantially increase contrast between a material of interest and its substrate, improving detectability under varying surface textures and lighting conditions.

For AI-ready optical inspection workflows, UV fluorescence provides two pragmatic advantages:

- a) It reduces ambiguity in image annotation by improving separability between TIM and background materials.
- b) It increases robustness to color and texture variation of underlying package surfaces, solder masks, cold plates, and surrounding components.

2.3 Computer vision and deep learning for defect and quality inspection

Automatic optical inspection (AOI) has an extensive body of work in electronics manufacturing, with deep learning increasingly used for defect detection, segmentation, and classification due to its ability to learn hierarchical features and reduce hand-crafted rule complexity [13]. Modern approaches often use robust feature extractors (for example, residual networks) and task-specific heads for detection and segmentation [15]. For real-time or near-real-time industrial inspection, recent methods emphasize multiscale feature fusion and efficient inference [14]. In contexts where defect samples are rare or expensive to label, anomaly detection datasets and methods have become important, including widely used benchmarks supporting unsupervised and semi-supervised approaches [16].

Within this landscape, UV-enhanced TIM inspection can be treated as an image understanding problem with multiple valid task formulations (for example, segmentation, classification, or anomaly detection). This paper focuses on the dataset specification and the empirical thermal evidence supporting learnability and operational value, while avoiding disclosure of any proprietary decision logic.

2.4 Infrared thermography as a complementary validation modality

Infrared (IR) thermography is widely used for qualitative thermal validation in electronics and systems engineering, particularly for identifying hotspots, heat spreading patterns, and cooling effectiveness. In typical service-like conditions, IR imagery should be interpreted as apparent temperature rather than absolute temperature, because apparent temperature depends on emissivity, surface finish, viewing angle, reflections, and camera calibration assumptions [8]. Nevertheless, IR thermography is highly valuable for comparative interpretation when camera position, palette settings, and scene composition are controlled.

In this work, IR thermography is used as a visually interpretable companion to on-die and on-board digital sensors. It provides an additional layer of evidence about where thermal energy is flowing (or failing to flow) within the cooling path, and it is included in the dataset publication plan [18].

3. Problem statement and objectives

The practical objective is to enable an AI-assisted workflow to assess whether there is a thermal-contact issue due to insufficient or defective TIM application, using a photo or video captured during the TIM application stage (and, where available, supporting telemetry and benchmark context).

Operationally, the target use cases include:

1. A repeatable quality gate during repair or refurbishment: after applying TIM and before reassembly, capture UV (and optionally visible) image/video; the workflow produces an acceptance decision and rework guidance.
2. Dataset-driven improvement of remote diagnostics: correlate optical evidence with telemetry and benchmarks to reduce root-cause ambiguity in remote triage.
3. Standardization: reduce variability across technicians by using consistent, data-backed criteria rather than purely subjective inspection.

Scientific objectives include:

a) Define an acquisition protocol that yields repeatable, label-friendly optical data under UV and visible illumination.

b) Establish an empirical basis linking TIM condition to measurable thermal and performance outcomes under comparable load.

c) Define the dataset artifacts and documentation required to support reproducibility and independent evaluation.

d) Document how IR thermography can serve as a qualitative cross-check to validate heat spreading and dissipation behavior.

4. Dataset design and acquisition protocol

4.1 Data modalities included in the dataset specification

A robust dataset for UV-enhanced TIM inspection should include four categories of artifacts, ideally time-aligned or at least stage-aligned:

A. Optical data (UV and visible)

1. UV fluorescence images: captured under consistent UV-A illumination (for example, 365–395 nm) to maximize contrast between TIM signal and substrate.
2. Visible-light images: captured under controlled white illumination to support non-UV field conditions and domain robustness.
3. Short videos: optional but valuable for capturing spreading dynamics and coverage evolution.

B. Telemetry logs

High-frequency sensor logs (temperature, power, clocks, fan speeds, system temperatures) provide outcome evidence and a reproducible thermal signature under a defined benchmark load.

C. Benchmark outputs

Benchmark results and configuration information document the load profile and end-user-visible performance impact.

D. IR thermography footage

IR video captured during benchmark execution provides qualitative validation of spatial heat flow and dissipation activation (for example, heatsink fin thermal activation), with the interpretation caveat that measurements are apparent-temperature in typical non-laboratory conditions [8].

4.2 Capture protocol and metadata requirements

For reproducibility, each capture session should record:

- Stage label (for example, before/after; fan profile mode).
- Ambient room temperature and any independent ambient reference (in this work, 20.2–20.9°C; a visible thermometer overlay is present in a companion video).
- Benchmark name and settings (for example, Unigine Superposition 1080p Extreme).
- Camera and illumination setup descriptors (UV source type/wavelength band, distance, angle, exposure settings if available).

- Any notes about assembly (for example, cleaning steps, reassembly torque practice where applicable).

Figure 1: UV vs visible example frames illustrating TIM visibility and contrast.

Figure 2: Example IR frame with annotated regions of interest (ROIs) (heatsink fins, PCB hotspot zones).

Figure 3: Timeline alignment concept (telemetry load segment and corresponding IR timeframe).

5. Case study: thermal telemetry and IR evidence across four stages

5.1 Experimental platform and conditions

This case study demonstrates that thermal interface optimization produces measurable and repeatable changes in thermal and performance outcomes under comparable GPU load and board power. The purpose is to establish a strong empirical basis that motivates learning from optical evidence and validates that the thermal-contact condition is a dominant explanatory factor.

Four stages were recorded:

Stage A: Old TIM, automatic fan profile

Stage B: Old TIM, full fan profile

Stage C: New TIM, automatic fan profile

Stage D: New TIM, full fan profile

The intervention consisted of replacement of aged baseline interface materials with:

(i) KRYO33 high-performance thermal paste (manufacturer-stated thermal conductivity >13 W/m·K) on the GPU die.

(ii) K5 PRO Mt. Olympus Edition viscous thermal paste (manufacturer-stated thermal conductivity >15 W/m·K) on memory/VRM contact regions.

These manufacturer-stated conductivity values provide useful context, but thermal outcomes under controlled load remain the decision-relevant validation signal for contact quality in situ, especially given known challenges in cross-material comparability [3], [17]. The specific materials used in this case study (KRYO33 and K5 PRO Mt. Olympos Edition) are electrically non-conductive, eliminating the risk of short circuits during application.

Ambient room temperature was monitored independently during all tests and remained in the range 20.2–20.9°C. In the companion visible-light video that accompanies the dataset, a digital thermometer is continuously visible in the lower-left corner, providing a persistent ambient reference. Any temperature variations observed in system telemetry beyond this narrow ambient band are attributable to the thermal state of the computer and its cooling path rather than external environmental drift.

Instrumentation included:

- a) High-frequency system telemetry logs (2-second sampling) comprising 457 sensor channels per timestamp.
- b) Benchmark execution using a repeatable GPU-heavy workload (Unigine Superposition 1080p Extreme).
- c) Infrared (IR) thermography video monitoring the GPU region (heatsink fins and adjacent PCB), central processing unit (CPU) area, and motherboard during benchmark execution. Three IR artifacts were produced: “Before Repaste – Fans Auto”, “Before Repaste – Fans 100%”, and “After Repaste – Combined Run” (recording both fan-profile benchmarks sequentially: automatic/normal, then full).

5.2 Data segmentation and IR asset timing

Telemetry processing followed a load segmentation procedure based on GPU power thresholding. Load segments were isolated using a GPU power threshold (>200 W). For clarity for non-specialists, this paper reports peak (maximum) values observed during each benchmark load window (Tables 1–4). Steady-state statistics (e.g., computed over the final 30% of each load segment) can also be derived from the raw telemetry logs included in the dataset [18].

5.3.1 Benchmark Performance Comparison

The intervention resulted in a consistent uplift in synthetic benchmark scores. Under the automatic fan profile, the score increased by 2.1%, while under maximum fan speed, a gain of 0.8% was recorded. More importantly, the GPU Utilization reached a more stable 99%, and Maximum Power Draw increased by 2.5% (+8.6W), confirming that the GPU was previously hitting thermal limits that prevented it from utilizing its full power budget. Tables 1 and 2 summarize the benchmark score, average frame rate (frames per second, FPS), and peak GPU temperature for both fan profiles (automatic and 100% fan).

Table 1. Benchmark score comparison before vs. after repaste (GPU fans auto).

Benchmark Score: Before vs After Repaste (GPU Fans Auto)			
Metric	Before Repaste	After Repaste	Difference
Score	11227	11471	↑+244 (+2.1%)
FPS (avg)	83.98	85.80	↑+1.82 (+2.1%)
GPU °C (max)	73.0 °C	68.0 °C	↓-5.0 °C (-7.4%)
GPU Utilization (max)	98%	99%	↑ +1%

Table 2. Benchmark score comparison before vs. after repaste (GPU fans 100%).

Benchmark Score: Before vs After Repaste (GPU Fans 100%)			
Metric	Before Repaste	After Repaste	Difference
Score	11363	11451	↑+88 (+0.8%)
FPS (avg)	84.99	85.65	↑+0.66 (+0.8%)
GPU °C (max)	70.0 °C	58.0 °C	↓-12.0 °C (-17.1%)

5.3.2 Detailed Thermal Metrics (Peak / Maximum Values)

The most significant improvements are observed in the GPU hotspot and VRAM junction peak temperatures. Under automatic fan control, the hotspot maximum dropped by 18.1°C (-19.4%) and the VRAM junction maximum dropped by 16.0°C (-17.8%); in parallel, the peak hotspot-to-core temperature delta was reduced by 64.3% (from 19.9°C down to 7.1°C) (Table 3). Under maximum fan speed (100%), the hotspot maximum dropped by 16.0°C (-18.0%) and the VRAM junction maximum dropped by 15.0°C (-17.4%); the peak hotspot-to-core delta decreased by 11.8°C (from 18.9°C to 7.1°C) (Table 4).

Table 3. Peak thermal metrics before vs. after repaste (fans auto).

GPU Temps: Before vs After Repaste (Fans Auto)			
Metric	Before Repaste	After Repaste	Difference
GPU Temperature Max	73.2 °C	67.9 °C	↓-5.3 °C (-7.3%)
GPU Hotspot Max	93.1 °C	75.0 °C	↓-18.1 °C (-19.4%)
GPU VRAM Junction Max	90.0 °C	74.0 °C	↓-16.0 °C (-17.8%)
GPU Power Max	338.08 W	346.68 W	↑+8.6 W (+2.5%)
GPU1 Fan Average	1366 RPM	1281 RPM	↓-85 RPM (-6.2%)
GPU2 Fan Average	1367 RPM	1282 RPM	↓-85 RPM (-6.2%)
Delta (Hotspot - GPU Temp) Max	19.9 °C	7.1 °C	↓-12.8 °C (-64.3%)

Table 4. Peak thermal metrics before vs. after repaste (fans 100%).

GPU Temps: Before vs After Repaste (GPU Fans 100%)			
Metric	Before Repaste	After Repaste	Difference
GPU Temperature Max	70.0 °C	65.8 °C	↓-4.2 °C (-6.0%)
GPU Hotspot Max	88.9 °C	72.9 °C	↓-16.0 °C (-18.0%)
GPU VRAM Junction Max	86.0 °C	71.0 °C	↓-15.0 °C (-17.4%)
GPU Power Max	338.08 W	346.68 W	↑+8.6 W (+2.5%)
GPU1 Fan Average	2215 RPM	2218 RPM	↓-3 RPM (-0.1%)
GPU2 Fan Average	2217 RPM	2220 RPM	↓-3 RPM (-0.1%)
Delta (Hotspot - GPU Temp) Max	18.9 °C	7.1 °C	↓-11.8 °C (-64.3%)

5.3.3 Operational Efficiency and Acoustic Impact

Efficiency gains are further evidenced by the reduction in fan speeds required to maintain lower temperatures. Under the automatic profile, average fan speeds decreased by ~85

revolutions per minute (RPM) (−6.2%), effectively reducing the system's acoustic footprint while operating at a higher power level .

5.5 Interpretation of telemetry results

Several consistent patterns emerge:

1. Large reductions in hotspot and VRAM junction temperatures. Across both fan profiles, peak GPU hotspot temperature decreased by 18.1°C (fans auto) and 16.0°C (fans 100%), while peak VRAM junction temperature decreased by 16.0°C (fans auto) and 15.0°C (fans 100%) (Tables 3 and 4). In addition, the peak hotspot-to-core delta decreased by 12.8°C (fans auto) and 11.8°C (fans 100%), indicating substantially improved thermal-contact uniformity.
2. While GPU power draw remains relatively stable across all stages, a measurable increase of +8.6 W (+2.5%) was observed in the post-intervention compared to the baseline. This upward shift in power consumption, occurring simultaneously with a massive reduction in junction temperatures, indicates that the system is no longer constrained by thermal limits.
The fact that the GPU consumes more power while operating significantly cooler confirms that the lower temperatures are not an artifact of reduced workload, but a direct result of minimized thermal contact resistance and superior heat transfer efficiency. Essentially, the card has regained the thermal headroom required to sustain higher power levels without triggering protective throttling mechanisms.
3. Lower fan duty at comparable load (automatic fan profile). Under the automatic fan profile, average GPU fan speed decreased by approximately 85 RPM (−6.2%) after repaste (Table 3). This indicates potential acoustic benefit and reduced fan wear while maintaining lower peak temperatures under comparable load.
4. Clock behavior and stability. Telemetry logs indicate improved stability of GPU clock behavior after repaste under sustained load, consistent with increased thermal headroom. Detailed time-series evidence is available in the raw telemetry files included in the dataset [18].
5. System-level thermal effects and ambient confounding control. Secondary reductions in CPU package temperature, VR VCC temperature, and motherboard temperature are observed, especially under full fan conditions. While motherboard temperature dropped by about 3°C, likely due to reduced radiant heat from localized PCB hot-spots, this small internal ambient shift accounts for only a fraction of the up to ~18°C reductions observed in peak hotspot and VRAM junction temperatures (Tables 3 and 4). Additionally, room temperature was independently monitored and remained within 20.2–20.9°C across all runs (documented in the companion video via the continuously visible digital thermometer). Therefore, the dominant explanatory factor for the observed deltas is the thermal interface intervention rather than external ambient conditions.

5.6 IR thermography observations and interpretation

The IR thermography footage provides qualitative but highly informative confirmation of changes in spatial heat flow and dissipation behavior. Because IR measurements in this context represent apparent temperature, the footage is best used for comparative interpretation rather than absolute temperature claims [8].

Heat transfer to the dissipation surface becomes more effective after repaste. Representative “before” frames show stronger concentration of heat in PCB-adjacent regions around the GPU and nearby components, with heatsink fin surfaces appearing comparatively less activated [18]. In the “after” footage, overall component sensor temperatures are substantially lower (Tables 3 & 4), yet the heatsink fin stack appears hotter and more uniformly activated under the automatic/normal fan profile. The hotter appearance of the heatsink fins in the “after” footage (despite lower core temperatures) confirms that thermal energy is successfully reaching the dissipation surface, where it can be removed by convection. This is consistent with reduced interface thermal resistance and improved coupling between GPU/VRAM heat sources and the heatsink.

5.7 Benchmark outcome context

In the benchmark workload used to generate the telemetry logs, the Unigine Superposition 1080p Extreme score increased from 11,227 to 11,471 under the automatic fan profile (+2.1%), and from 11,363 to 11,451 under maximum fan speed (+0.8%) (Tables 1 and 2). This links thermal interface quality to end-user-visible performance outcomes, supporting the value of standardized inspection and repeatable service practice.

6. Relevance to AI-enabled remote diagnostic workflows

This case study is positioned within a broader research direction focused on AI-enabled remote fault diagnosis and service standardization for computing systems. In that context, UV-enhanced inspection can serve as an evidence channel that complements telemetry: telemetry demonstrates that a thermal issue exists; optical evidence can support determination of whether a TIM application issue is a plausible root cause before reassembly.

The dataset described in this paper is explicitly designed to support research into computer vision models that can learn the relationship between visually observable TIM application quality and outcome evidence recorded via telemetry and benchmark behavior. This public version intentionally avoids disclosure of any proprietary decision logic, feature orchestration, or scoring mechanisms that may be subject to IP protection, while retaining a complete and verifiable empirical basis and a reproducible dataset structure.

7. Safety and operational considerations

UV-A illumination is commonly used for fluorescence inspection, but safe handling practices are required, including eye protection and controlled exposure duration consistent with standard UV inspection environments [10], [11]. The specific materials used in this case study

(KRYO33 and K5 PRO Mt. Olympus Edition) are electrically non-conductive, eliminating the risk of short circuits during application.

8. Dataset publication plan

The dataset created for this work will be published separately [18]. The planned content includes:

A. Optical data

UV images and videos, visible images and videos, and capture metadata.

B. IR thermography data

IR videos retained in their original form.

C. Telemetry and benchmark data

Raw sensor logs and benchmark outputs, plus scripts used for load segmentation and peak-metric extraction (maximum-value summary tables).

9. Limitations and future work

1. IR thermography is apparent-temperature in typical service contexts. Without controlled emissivity targets and laboratory-like calibration, IR frames must be interpreted comparatively rather than absolutely [8]. Nonetheless, they are valuable for spatial verification of heat dissipation behavior.
2. Dataset breadth and generalization. Generalization across hardware platforms requires diversity in substrates and geometries. Future dataset expansions should cover multiple GPU/CPU packages and cooling assemblies.
3. Field usability constraints. Capturing clear pre-assembly imagery can be constrained by mechanical accessibility. Future work should explore guided capture procedures suitable for technicians and non-expert users.

10. Conclusion

This white paper proposes a practical, scientifically grounded approach for UV-enhanced visual verification of TIM application quality within a dataset-driven AI research program for remote computer diagnostics. The empirical case study demonstrates that thermal interface optimization materially reduces peak hotspot and VRAM junction temperatures under comparable load and board power (hotspot max: -18.1°C with fans auto and -16.0°C with fans 100%; VRAM junction max: -16.0°C with fans auto and -15.0°C with fans 100%), while also reducing the peak hotspot-to-core temperature delta by 64.3% (Tables 3 and 4). Benchmark performance increased by +2.1% (fans auto) and +0.8% (fans 100%) (Tables 1 and 2), and under the automatic profile average fan speed decreased by ~ 85 RPM (-6.2%) while maintaining lower peak temperatures (Table 3). Complementary IR thermography provides qualitative confirmation that heat is more effectively reaching the heatsink dissipation surface after repaste, consistent with reduced interface thermal resistance. These findings substantiate the value of a UV-enabled inspection workflow and

an AI-ready multimodal dataset as components of a broader remote diagnostic and service standardization framework.

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